

DNA-Interacting Agents in Cancer Chemotherapy and Cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline Derivatives^Ψ

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Cancer chemotherapeutic agents have been briefly reviewed with an emphasis on DNA-binders. Cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivatives which we developed on CPK-molecular model studies, have been discussed. The synthesis of a few new cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolines is also described.

In modern times cancer has become one of the worst killers of human being all over the world. In developed countries it is the second largest killer of people¹. In India, it can be considered as a major killer. The total number of cancer cases in India is estimated for the year 2001 to be 806000². Although radiation and surgery are used where the tumour is accessible, the use of chemotherapy³ for the treatment of cancer has become increasingly important from the time of introduction of nitrogen mustard for the treatment of lymphomas and of estrogens for the treatment of carcinoma of the prostate and the breast in the nineteenforties. Today the chemicals which are used in the treatment of cancer can be subdivided in the following major groups : (i) alkylating agents (*N*-mustard 1, melphalan 2, chlorambucil 3, cyclophosphamide 4), (ii) antimetabolites (5-fluorouracil 5, 6-mercaptopurine 6, 6-thioguanine 7, ara-C 8, methotrexate 9), (iii) DNA-binding agents (actinomycin 10, daunomycin 11, adriamycin 12), (iv) natural products (vinblastine 13, vincristine 14, taxol 15) and (v) miscellaneous agents (*cis*-platin 16, hydroxyurea 17).

In this article we wish to review some of the DNA-interacting agents which have found extensive application in cancer chemotherapy, the new analogs which are being developed with the hope that they will have better efficacy and less toxicities, and our own work on cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivatives which are designed to bind with double-helical DNA.

Compounds which bind to DNA by intercalation, electrostatic and other forces, and inhibit vital enzymic processes in the cell, e.g. inhibition of DNA and RNA syntheses etc., leading to cellular death, have played a very important role in cancer chemotherapy. These compounds which we refer to as DNA-interacting agents, or DNA-

binders, have been of both natural product and synthetic origin. One of the earliest to be isolated and studied extensively has been actinomycin-D. Actinomycin-D (10) was first isolated in 1940 by Waksman and Woodruff from *Streptomyces*⁴. The drug has been extensively used in the case of Wilms tumour, some testicular tumours, and choriocarcinoma⁵. The drug binds to double helical DNA in GC-rich regions. It inhibits RNA synthesis at relatively low concentrations and at high concentrations inhibits DNA synthesis. The anthracycline antibiotics, daunomycin (daunomycin) (11) and adriamycin (doxorubicin) (12) were isolated from *Streptomyces peucetius var. caesius*⁶⁻⁹. The two compounds have the same basic structures consisting of an aglycone and an amino sugar, daunosamine. Chemically they differ from each other by the presence of an extra hydroxyl group in the aglycone part of adriamycin. However, this makes a great difference in the biological activities of these two compounds. Adriamycin has become one of the most important drugs used in the clinic. It is a broad spectrum drug useful in the treatment of Hodgkin's disease, non-Hodgkin's lymphomas, acute leukemia, adenocarcinoma of the breast, lung and ovary, soft tissue sarcomas, neuroblastoma, and the adenocarcinoma of the thyroid¹⁰⁻¹³. The use of daunomycin is however more limited to the treatment of leukemia. Because of their importance, extensive investigations have been made in the mechanism of action of these compounds. Both daunomycin and adriamycin interact with DNA *in vitro*. Apparent binding constants of the order of 2.9×10^6 and $2.8 \times 10^6 M^{-1}$ were found for the interaction between DNA and daunomycin and adriamycin respectively¹⁴. Both daunomycin and adriamycin inhibit DNA and RNA synthesis in varying isolated polymerase systems. The inhibition is due to the interaction of the drug with DNA rather than direct inhibition of the enzyme¹⁵. The biochemical and biological effects of both daunomycin and adriamycin can be explained on the basis of the interaction of the drugs with double-helical DNA by intercalative forces and ionic interactions¹⁶. In living cell nuclei, 99.8% of adriamycin was found to be bound to DNA¹⁷ whereas from human tumour biopsy, 80% of adriamycin was found to be associated with DNA¹⁸. Due to adriamycin-binding to DNA, inhibition of topoisomerase II activity¹⁹ and topoisomerase-induced DNA strand breaks were observed^{20,21}. The quinone function in both adriamycin and daunomycin is a redox function and is capable of generating reactive oxygen species (superoxide and radicals) which have been implicated both in tumour cell cytotoxicity and cardiotoxicity^{22,23}. Under nonenzymatic condition, *in vitro* formation of a quinone methide (20) from adriamycin due to glycosidic bond cleavage and its interaction with the 2-amino group of the 2'-deoxyguanosine of DNA leading to interstrand cross-links of DNA has been suggested²⁴

(Scheme 1). The cross-link contains the adriamycin chromophore intercalated at the GpC site of cross-linking. Maximal stoichiometry of the cross-link was one per 11-20 base pair. The possibility of interstrand DNA cross-links being associated with the clinical mechanism of action of this drug has been suggested.

Scheme 1

Very recently Koch and coworkers²⁵ have studied the interaction of the antitumour drugs adriamycin and dauno-

Scheme 2

mycin with the self-complementary DNA oligonucleotide GCGCGCGC, (GC)₄ in the presence of the reducing agent dithiothreitol, the oxidising agent hydrogen peroxide or the alkylating agent formaldehyde (Scheme 2). They observed the formation of similar mixture of DNA-drug adducts as the major product, being an adduct of duplex DNA containing two molecules of anthracycline. From their studies they concluded that reductive activation of adriamycin in the presence of oxygen led to hydrogen peroxide which oxidized the drug or constituents in the reaction mixture to formaldehyde (24). The formaldehyde then coupled the drug to DNA. A molecular structure with each anthracycline intercalated at a 5'-CpG-3' site and covalently bound from its 3'-amino group to a 2-amino group of a 2'-deoxyguanosine nucleotide through a methylene group (derived from the formaldehyde) was proposed (see Scheme 2).

Although adriamycin has been one of the most important drugs used in cancer chemotherapy, its use has been limited due to drug-cumulative cardiotoxicity and bone marrow depression. Other toxic effects, e.g. alopecia, stomatitis, vomiting etc. have also been observed. In order to eliminate these toxic effects and develop some improved drugs, various chemical modifications have been made during the

last two decades leading to the development of hundreds of new analogs with limited improved chemotherapeutic activities²⁶⁻²⁸.

Recent studies report the synthesis of a 3'-trifluoromethyl analog²⁹ (26) of adriamycin and WP631, a bisanthracycline³⁰ (27) based on daunorubicin which show promising biological activities. Other anticancer drugs, which are of considerable interest and are known to bind to DNA, are 4'-(9-acridinylamino)methanesulfon-*m*-anisidide (*m*-AMSA, 28)³¹ and anthracenediones (mitoxantrone, 29)³². Due to limitation of space, further discussions on these interesting compounds could not be undertaken. The readers are referred to the references.

Recently, some interesting molecules have been developed which bind to specific regions of DNA and thereby exert their chemotherapeutic properties. Ditercalinium (30) is one such molecule which is a bifunctional intercalator with antitumour activity and binds preferentially to the GC-rich regions of DNA³³⁻³⁶. The molecule is characterized by the presence of two chromophoric sites which increase its binding affinity and a central linker which prevents the intramolecular stacking of the two aromatic rings. The linker also increases the life-time of the complex by hampering the displacement of the ligand along the DNA helix. Also, the aminoalkyl chain increases the water solubility and enhances the DNA affinity through electrostatic interactions.

In connection with our studies on the development of cancer chemotherapeutic agents which will be effective by their binding to DNA, we devised ad hoc on the basis of CPK molecular models, a cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivative (31) that would be expected (i) to bind to the GC pairs of double-stranded DNA in the major groove by hydrogen-bond only, (ii) not to be electrostatically attracted to the phosphates of the backbone and (iii) to stack parallel to the base pairs.

Fig 1

Fig. 1 shows the complex between the cyclopenta[*f*]-isoquinoline derivative (31) and the GC pair of DNA duplex such that the aminoproton of cytosine donates a hydrogen bond to the C-3 carbonyl group of the isoquinolone and the amide proton of the side-chain donates a hydrogen bond to the N-7 of the guanine. Such a novel structure is not present in any of the known DNA-binding antibiotics. We have synthesized 31 through a number of steps^{38,39} as shown in Scheme 3. The cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivative (31) showed weak cytotoxicities only. It inhibited by 25% the growth of L1210 mouse leukemia and CCRF-CEM human lymphoblastoid cells at concentration of 1.0×10^{-4} and 8.0×10^{-5} M respectively. However, it fulfilled the predictions which were made about its binding with DNAs and polynucleotides⁴⁰. Thus, from difference spectral studies it was observed that 31 binds to native calf thymus DNA better than to denatured DNA. Moreover, it interacted with synthetic polydeoxyribonucleotides containing only GC pairs more effectively than with AT polymers. Also, the tricyclic moiety was essential for binding and the side-chain greatly enhanced the interaction.

Scheme 3 Reagents . (i) $\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{Cl}$, AlCl_3 , (ii) KCN , $\text{H}_2\text{O-EtOH}$, (iii) HCl , (iv) EtOH , $\text{H}^+ \rightarrow \text{pH } 8$, (v) $\text{Et}_3\text{O}^+\text{BF}_4^-$ in CH_2Cl_2 , (vi) LAH , (vii) PBr_3 , (viii) NaCN in DMF , (ix) HCl , (x) FSO_3H , (xi) $(\text{CO}_2\text{Et})_2$, NaOEt , (xii) $\text{BrCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, KOBu^t , (xiii), 25% HCl in a sealed tube, 140° , (xiv) EtOH , H_2SO_4 , (xv) NH_3 in EtOH , (xvi) NaBH_4 and (xvii) HCl in gl. HOAc

The interaction between 31 and calf thymus DNA was demonstrated by the effect of 31 on the thermal transition temperature (T_m) of native calf thymus DNA. A small but significant increase in T_m of 3.5° was observed. Also in the presence of 31 although a small increase in T_m of 3° was observed for poly(dG) poly(dC), no such change was seen in the case of poly(dA) poly(dT). The interaction of 31 with DNA was further confirmed by its effect on the inhibition of RNA synthesis by a DNA-dependent RNA polymerase

from *E. coli*. More than 35% inhibition of RNA synthesis was observed in the presence of 31 (4×10^{-4}) with calf thymus DNA as template (3.3×10^{-5} M). Also, a higher inhibition of RNA synthesis was observed when poly(deoxyguanine-deoxycytosine) [poly(dG-dC)] was used as a template than when poly(deoxyadenine-deoxythymine)-[poly(dA-dT)] was used. However, 31 caused no inhibition of DNA synthesis by a DNA-dependent DNA polymerase obtained from HeLa cells. From equilibrium dialysis experiments, for the interaction of native calf thymus DNA with 31, binding constant value, k_{app} (M^{-1}), of 1.14×10^4 was obtained and the number of nucleotides per binding site was 26. Thus, it has been possible for us from molecular model studies to develop a small molecule which binds to double stranded DNA through hydrogen bonding. The compound also showed considerable GC specificity.

Encouraged by our success we also designed from molecular model studies, a cyclopenta[*a*]naphthalene derivative (39) which we hoped would bind to double stranded DNA with AT specificity. We have synthesized and carried out binding studies of 39 with DNAs and polynucleotides⁴⁰. We found that the cyclopenta[*a*]naphthalene interacted with DNAs and poly(deoxyribonucleotides) albeit very weakly. However, its interactions with them were completely non-specific.

In continuation of our above studies, we have recently undertaken a programme to synthesize a number of deriva-

Scheme 4. Reagents : (i), (ii) CH_3I , (iii), (iv) 1N NaOH solution, (v) 25% HCl , (vi) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$ and (vii) $\text{Br-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$.

tives and analogs of 31 with the purpose of determining the structural parameters which are essential for the binding of 31 with DNAs and polynucleotides with the hope that a better derivative could be developed which will bind to DNAs with higher binding constants and considerable GC specificity. With that purpose, we have synthesized a number of cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivatives as shown in Scheme 4. The synthesis of compounds 37, 41, and 42 have already been reported³⁷. The methoiodides 43 and 44 were obtained from 41 and 42 respectively, by stirring with methyl iodide at room temperature. From ¹H nmr, 44 was seen as a mixture of 5*H* and 7*H* isomers (see Experimental). Whereas treatment of the methoiodide 44 with 1 *N* sodium hydroxide solution led to elimination of hydrogen iodide leading to 46, similar treatment of 43 led to the de-ethylated product 45. Presumably, the higher acidity of C₇-H in 44 (versus 43) was conducive to the elimination of hydrogen iodide leading to the conjugated system of 46. Such lack of acidity of C₇-H in 43 led to the elimination of ethyl iodide giving rise to the cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolone 45. The cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-5-one 37 could also be de-methylated by heating with 25% hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube to compound 40.

6-Carboethoxymethyl-3-ethoxy-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7*H*-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-5-one (38) was synthesized from 37 by treatment with diethyl oxalate and sodium ethoxide and subsequent reaction of the oxalyl derivative (38) with ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of sodium ethoxide³⁸. Compound 38 on heating with benzyl bromide yielded 47, whereas on heating with ethyl bromoacetate, 48 was formed. Compounds 47 and 48 were tested for their cytotoxic activities against L1210 mouse leukemia and CCRF-CEM human lymphoblastoid cells in culture⁴¹. The IC₅₀s for compound 47 were 2.2×10^{-5} (CCRF-CEM) and 8.9×10^{-6} *M* (L1210), whereas that for 48 were 8.0×10^{-5} (CCRF-CEM) and 7.5×10^{-5} *M* (L1210). The DNA-binding studies with the synthesized cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline derivatives are projected for the future.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Thomas-Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on Varian EM-360 and Bruker DPX-300 spectrometers in solvents as indicated with tetramethylsilane as internal reference. Column chromatography was done on silica gel (60–120 mesh). Elemental analyses were done by Spang Microanalytical Laboratory, Ann Arbor, Mich, U.S.A.

8-Methyl-5,6-dihydro-2 H,7 H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-3,5-dione (40) : 3-Ethoxy-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7*H*-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-5-one (37; 500 mg, 2.07 mmol) was heated with 25% HCl (20 ml) at 140° for 10 h in a sealed tube. The crystalline solid which separated out on

cooling was filtered and crystallized from 95% ethanol as yellow needles (300 mg, 1.4 mmol, 68%), m.p. 345°d (Found : C, 73.20; H, 5.14; N, 6.51. C₁₃H₁₁NO₂ requires : C, 73.23; H, 5.20; N, 6.57%); ν_{\max} 3480, 1690, 1645, 1630, 1605 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃; 300 MHz) 2.40 (3H, s, C₈-CH₃), 2.73 (2H, m, CH₂-Ar), 3.09 (2H, m, -CH₂-CO-Ar), 7.84 (1H, s, C₉-H), 7.9 (1H, s, C₄-H), 8.78 (1H, s, C₁-H), 11.25 (1H, br s, N-H).

3-Ethoxy-5-hydroxy-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7 H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline methoiodide (43) : A mixture of 3-ethoxy-5-hydroxy-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7*H*-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline (41; 200 mg, 0.82 mmol) and methyl iodide (5 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 3 days. The methyl iodide was then removed and the residue was digested with hot benzene (2 × 5 ml) and filtered to yield a glistening white solid (300 mg, 0.78 mmol, 95%), m.p. 190–92° (partly decomposed) (Found : C, 50.06; H, 5.25; N, 3.71. C₁₆H₂₀NIO₂ requires : C, 49.86; H, 5.19; N, 3.64%); ν_{\max} 3310, 1650, 1620 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃; 300 MHz) 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.48 (3H, s, C₈-CH₃), 2.10–3.34 (4H, m, C₆-H and C₇-H), 4.21 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 4.57 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃), 5.69–5.75 (2H, m, C₅-H, OH), 7.89 (1H, s, C₉-H), 7.93 (1H, s, C₄-H), 9.68 (1H, s, C₁-H).

3-Ethoxy-8-methyl-7(5)H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline methoiodide (44) : A mixture of 3-ethoxy-8-methyl-7(5)*H*-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline (42; 200 mg, 0.89 mmol) and methyl iodide (1 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 12 h when yellow solid separated out, which was filtered and digested with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and filtered again to yield a deep yellow powder (325 mg, 0.88 mmol, 99%); m.p.>350° (Found : C, 52.18; H, 4.91; N, 3.76. C₁₆H₁₈NIO requires : C, 52.26; H, 4.90; N, 3.81%); ν_{\max} 1 650 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃; 300 MHz) 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 6 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃), 2.59 and 2.63 (3H, 2s, C₈-CH₃), 3.72 and 3.96 (2H, 2s, C₇-CH₂), 4.18 and 4.23 (3H, 2s, N-CH₃), 4.62 (2H, q, *J* 6 Hz, -O-CH₂CH₃), 6.96–8.15 (4H, m, C₄-H, C₅-H, C₆-H and C₉-H), 9.69 and 9.79 (1H, 2s, C₁-H).

5-Hydroxy-2,8-dimethyl-5,6-dihydro-7 H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-3(2 H)-one (45) : To the methoiodide 43 (1g, 2.6 mmol) dissolved in water (160 ml), was added NaOH solution (1*N*; 300 ml) dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 5–10 min. It was then extracted with chloroform (3 × 100 ml). The chloroform extracts were combined, dried (anhydrous K₂CO₃), filtered, and the solvent was removed to yield a yellow solid which was purified by chromatography on silica gel (60–120 mesh) using eluent chloroform-methanol (10 : 1) to yield a bright yellow solid (200 mg, 0.87 mmol, 33%), crystallized from chloroform-methanol, m.p.>250° (Found : C, 73.16; H, 6.66; N, 6.14. C₁₄H₁₅NO₂ requires : C, 73.34; H, 6.59; N, 6.11%); ν_{\max} 3200, 1660,

1620 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6 + CDCl_3 ; 300 MHz) 1.86–3.05 (4H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}_2$, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}_2$), 2.23 (3H, s, $\text{C}_8\text{-CH}_3$), 3.74 (3H, s, N-CH_3), 5.16 (1H, br s, CHOH), 5.34–5.36 (1H, m, CHOH), 6.82 (1H, s, $\text{C}_9\text{-H}$), 8.08 (1H, s, $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$), 8.50 (1H, s, $\text{C}_1\text{-H}$).

3-Ethoxy-2,8-dimethylcyclopenta[*f*]isoquinoline (46) : The methiodide (44; 140 mg, 0.38 mmol) dissolved in water (50 ml), was added dropwise to a solution of NaOH (1 N; 50 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere when an orange colored solid separated out immediately. The mixture was extracted with chloroform (3 \times 50 mmol) to obtain a red solution. It was washed with water (2 \times 50 ml) and dried (anhydrous K_2CO_3). After removal of the solvent, a red solid was obtained (90 mg, 0.37 mmol, 97%), which was crystallized from chloroform in the cold as red crystals, m.p. 235–36° (Found : C, 80.11; H, 6.99; N, 5.96. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ requires : C, 80.30; H, 7.16; N, 5.85%); ν_{max} 1630, 1530, 1500 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3 ; 300 MHz), 1.56 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.52 (3H, s, $\text{C}_8\text{-CH}_3$), 3.79 (3H, s, N-CH_3), 4.34 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 6.50, 6.61 (2H, 2s, $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_9\text{-H}$), 7.01–7.11 (3H, m, $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$), 7.68 (1H, s, $\text{C}_1\text{-H}$).

2-Benzyl-6-carbethoxymethyl-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-3(2H)-5-dione (47) : A mixture of 6-carbethoxymethyl-3-ethoxy-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-5-one (38; 300 mg, 0.92 mmol) and benzyl bromide (5 ml) was heated at 100–110° for 1 h. Benzyl bromide was then removed from the mixture and the residue purified by chromatography over florisil, the eluent being chloroform-methanol (10 : 1), and crystallized from benzene as bright orange plates (350 mg, 0.90 mmol, 98%), m.p. 148–50° (Found : C, 73.92; H, 5.87; N, 3.36. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 74.02; H, 5.95; N, 3.6%); ν_{max} 1735, 1680, 1660, 1625 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3 ; 90 MHz) 1.29 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, $\text{C}_8\text{-CH}_3$), 2.63–3.35 (6H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}_2$, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}_2$, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 4.19 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 5.44 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.31–7.43 (6H, m, ArH), 8.02–8.04 (2H, 2s, ArH).

2,6-Dicarbethoxymethyl-8-methyl-5,6-dihydro-7H-cyclopenta[*f*]isoquinolin-3(2H)-5-dione (48) : Compound 38 (100 mg, 0.31 mmol) and ethyl bromoacetate (1g) were mixed, when a clear solution was formed. It was stirred at room temperature for 2 days and then heated at 90–100° for 4 h. The excess ethyl bromoacetate was then removed and the residue was crystallized from benzene as orange crystals (52 mg, 0.135 mmol, 44%), m.p. 166–67° (Found : C, 65.42; H, 6.07; N, 3.63. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_6$ requires : C, 65.44; H, 6.02; N, 3.63%); ν_{max} 1740, 1720, 1690, 1680, 1660, 1630 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6 + CDCl_3 ; 300 MHz) 1.23 and 1.28 (6H, 2t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_3$, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 2.57–3.01 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}_2$, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 4.11 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.22 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, $\text{N-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.98 (2H, s, $\text{N-CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$), 7.37 (1H,

s, $\text{C}_9\text{-H}$), 7.65 (1H, s, $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$), 8.68 (1H, s, $\text{C}_1\text{-H}$); m/z 385 (M^+), 357, 340.

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